

DEVELOPMENT OF TOLERANCE SKILLS OF STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes methodological approaches to developing tolerance, practical experiences in educational institutions, and the main problems in this process. The results of the study emphasize the importance of mutual respect and acceptance of cultural diversity among students, as well as the need to form these skills in the education system.

As a result of the comprehensive changes implemented in the Republic of Uzbekistan in the field of ensuring interethnic harmony and religious tolerance, Uzbekistan became the second country in the last 20 years to be removed from the list of "countries of particular concern" in the religious sphere by the US Department of State. In his speech at the 72nd session of the UN General Assembly, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev justified the need to adopt a special resolution entitled "Enlightenment and Religious Tolerance", saying, in particular: "This resolution is aimed at promoting tolerance and mutual respect, ensuring religious freedom, protecting the rights of believers, and preventing their discrimination."

Also, in the Address to the Oliy Majlis of our country in 2022, the President of our country, Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, emphasized that "Regardless of nationality, language and religion, every citizen who considers Uzbekistan his homeland and contributes to its prosperity will continue to be in the attention and respect of our state and society. We will mobilize all our strength and capabilities to further strengthen the atmosphere of interethnic friendship, harmony between religious confessions, and social tolerance." Tolerance means respect for the opinions of others, peaceful coexistence with them, and acceptance of differences and diversity. Students of higher educational institutions, in turn, must learn to work with different nationalities, cultures, religions and social groups. This article analyzes the importance, methods and problems of developing tolerance skills in higher educational institutions. The concept of tolerance is interpreted and defined differently in different languages. The national traditions, worldview and mentality of a particular nation play a role in this description. Also, the historical experiences of peoples can determine their attitude to these phenomena.

In Western countries, tolerance means showing kindness to a person or thing and creating an environment and conditions

for the viability of a new thought or idea. Also, tolerance as an activity is a form of resistance to the vices of religious extremism. As a result of historical development, tolerance has had its principles formed since ancient times, according to which it is based on the principles of seeing others as they are, not hurting them, and respecting their feelings.

The relevance of the problem of tolerance today is due to the fact that the values and principles necessary for common coexistence and free development, such as the ethics and strategy of non-violence, the idea of tolerance to alien and alien positions, values, cultures, the idea of dialogue and mutual understanding, the idea of reaching a mutually acceptable compromise, etc. come to the fore.

The culture of interethnic dialogue cannot be achieved without the formation of such a personal quality as tolerance in the subjects of the educational process, in the university micro-community, when studying and working together. Tolerance is a value of the socio-cultural system, it is the core of the existence of all humanity.

Tolerance is a principle, a guiding idea, a basic position in human relations, which is the main condition for success in communication and the organization of joint activities.

The formation of tolerant thinking and skills in students includes and encompasses:

- the absence of violence in relations between students and their attitude to nature
- the formation of students' appreciation of human rights, non-conflict relations, learning to communicate and cooperate, the presence of alternatives that provide students with the opportunity to choose, the creation of a positive atmosphere at school through an active tolerant attitude of parents to the problems of education and upbringing.

Seeing tolerance as a psychosocial characteristic of a person, scientists distinguish three subsystems in its structure:

1. Cognitive - human knowledge (the concept of tolerance itself, processes of tolerant interaction, etc.).
2. Emotional - specific feelings of a person (expressed in an emotional assessment of another's opinion, values, one's own feelings).
3. Activity-based - a tendency to various options for behavior (based on understanding, cooperation, compromise).

Tolerance is the ability to achieve success in communication and cooperation. The cognitive component of tolerance is determined by the "information field", the possession of which is how a person (group of people) behaves, based on personal (group) characteristics and the specifics of the socio-cultural environment.

Research scientist B.E. Rierdon classifies seven areas that are considered a specific methodological guide in the process of planning tolerance education. Preparing students for social life and educating an active lifestyle is based on the following:

- encouraging the development of the ability of younger school-age students to feel their needs, satisfy them without harming others;
- preparing them to assess their capabilities;
- developing the ability to act within their capabilities and strive to develop them;
- recognizing their own achievements and shortcomings;
- encouraging the manifestation of the initial manifestations of a critical approach;
- respect and be tolerant of the thoughts, actions, and customs of other students;
- learn certain rules and norms in society together with other students.

The methodology for studying the development of tolerance skills in students in higher education institutions requires a clear and systematic approach. The methodology of the study aims to identify effective methods in the educational process and measure the level of tolerance skills among students. This study used qualitative and quantitative research methods, since the process of developing tolerance skills depends on many social, cultural and psychological factors. The study was carried out using the following methods and techniques:

Participant selection: More than 200 students of higher education institutions and about 30 teachers participated in the study. Since the participants came from different social groups, national and religious backgrounds, special attention was paid to the differences between the participants in the study. This methodology made it possible to compare the levels of tolerance between specific groups.

Data collection tools:

Questionnaires: Questionnaires were developed to study the opinions of students on the development of tolerance. The questionnaires focused on social differences, cultural diversity, and other tolerance skills. Using this tool, students assessed their level of tolerance.

Interviews: Through interviews with teachers and students, opinions and experiences regarding the development of tolerance in the educational process were collected. In the interviews, questions were asked about how students perceive communication and cultural differences.

Group discussions: Group discussions were organized during the study. In these discussions, students were given the opportunity to discuss cultural diversity, relationships with others, and mutual respect. Group discussions helped to identify different approaches to developing tolerance.

Data analysis: Statistical methods (e.g., analysis and inference) were used in the data analysis. The results obtained based on questionnaires and tests were analyzed using statistical indicators. It was expected that the relationship between the level of tolerance of students and the methods used by teachers would be identified.

Ethical aspects of the study: Ethical aspects of the study were also taken into account. When involving participants in the study, their consent was obtained in advance, and the data were kept private and confidential. Questionnaires and interviews were conducted on a voluntary basis, and the participants' responses were analyzed anonymously.

Based on the research methodology, the effectiveness of educational processes and methods aimed at developing tolerance was assessed. These methods allowed us to determine whether the methodologies used to teach tolerance to students were effective or not. Based on this, the research recommended the most effective ways to improve tolerance skills among students.

The results of the study showed that students in higher education institutions pay great attention to the development of tolerance. However, some students face difficulties in accepting their cultural and religious differences.

Based on the questionnaires and interviews, the majority of students emphasized the importance of the teaching and learning process in interaction and working with different nationalities and religions. In most cases, tolerance skills are developed through dialogue and cultural activities. However, in some higher education institutions, such opportunities are not enough. From the results of the study, it can be understood that the following methods can be

effective for developing tolerance skills:

1. Organizing cultural events and seminars to increase tolerance among students. Such activities can strengthen mutual respect and understanding among students.

2. Organizing dialogue and group work between students from different social groups, helping to develop tolerance skills.

3. Organizing special courses or trainings aimed at developing tolerance, expanding students' knowledge and introducing them to issues of global citizenship, cultural understanding.

4. Organizing a mentoring system for students by experts or teachers with extensive experience.

Developing tolerance skills in higher education institutions plays an important role in ensuring social stability in society. Respect for each other, acceptance of cultural and religious diversity by students strengthens peace and harmony in society. At the same time, it is necessary to introduce effective teaching and learning methods in higher education institutions to develop tolerance. Programs and methods aimed at developing tolerance contribute to the personal and professional growth of students.

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